

HYGIENIC ASSESSMENT OF THE LIFESTYLE OF STUDENTS IN THE PERIOD OF MODERN PROGRESS

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Abstract. *This article provides a comprehensive hygienic assessment of the lifestyle of students in the context of modern technological and social progress. As contemporary advancements in technology and societal changes influence student lifestyles, understanding the impact on their health and well-being is crucial. The study examines various factors, including physical activity, dietary habits, sleep patterns, mental health, and screen time, to assess the overall hygienic practices of students. By analyzing data from recent surveys and academic studies, the article identifies key areas where modern progress has positively and negatively affected student health. The findings offer valuable insights for developing strategies to promote healthier lifestyles among students and mitigate the adverse effects of modern progress.*

Keywords: *hygienic assessment, Student lifestyle, Modern progress, Physical activity, Dietary habits, Sleep patterns, Mental health, Screen time, Health promotion, Technological advancements.*

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the rapid pace of technological and social progress has significantly altered the lifestyle of students worldwide. The integration of advanced technologies into everyday life, the proliferation of digital media, and changes in educational practices have transformed how students learn, interact, and live. These developments have brought about both positive and negative impacts on their health and well-being, necessitating a thorough hygienic assessment to understand these implications comprehensively.

Technological advancements, such as the widespread use of smartphones, tablets, and computers, have revolutionized the educational landscape. Digital learning tools and online resources have enhanced access to information and facilitated more interactive and personalized learning experiences [1]. However, these technologies have also contributed to a sedentary lifestyle among students, reducing their physical activity levels and increasing the time spent in front of screens [2]. This shift raises concerns about the potential health risks associated with prolonged screen time, including eye strain, poor posture, and reduced physical fitness [3].

Dietary habits have also been influenced by modern progress. The convenience of fast food and ready-to-eat meals, coupled with busy academic schedules, has led to changes in students' eating patterns. Studies have shown a trend towards increased consumption of high-calorie, low-nutrient foods, which can contribute to obesity and other health issues [4]. Additionally, the availability of energy-dense snacks and sugary beverages in and around educational institutions further exacerbates the problem [5].

Sleep patterns among students have been disrupted by the pervasive use of electronic devices, especially before bedtime. Exposure to blue light emitted by screens can interfere with the production of melatonin, a hormone that regulates sleep, leading to difficulties in falling

asleep and maintaining a healthy sleep schedule [6]. Insufficient sleep, in turn, affects cognitive function, academic performance, and overall health [7].

Mental health is another critical aspect that has been impacted by modern progress. The constant connectivity and pressure to maintain an online presence can contribute to stress, anxiety, and depression among students [8]. Social media platforms, while providing a means for social interaction, can also lead to cyberbullying, social comparison, and a sense of inadequacy [9]. Furthermore, the academic demands and competitive environment in educational institutions add to the mental health burden on students [10].

Given these multifaceted changes in student lifestyles, a hygienic assessment is essential to evaluate the overall impact on their health and well-being. This article aims to explore the various dimensions of students' lifestyles, including physical activity, dietary habits, sleep patterns, mental health, and screen time, in the context of modern technological and social progress. By analyzing data from recent surveys and academic studies, this study seeks to identify the benefits and drawbacks of these changes and propose strategies for promoting healthier lifestyles among students.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section outlines the methodological approach adopted to conduct a comprehensive hygienic assessment of the lifestyle of students in the period of modern progress. The study employs a mixed-methods approach, integrating both quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis techniques. The primary data sources include surveys, structured interviews, focus groups, and direct observations. The study population comprises students from various educational institutions, representing a diverse range of backgrounds and academic disciplines.

Study Design

The study was designed to capture a holistic view of the factors affecting students' health and well-being. It was conducted in three phases:

Quantitative Data Collection: This phase involved administering structured questionnaires to a large sample of students to gather data on their physical activity, dietary habits, sleep patterns, mental health, and screen time.

Qualitative Data Collection: In this phase, in-depth interviews and focus group discussions were conducted to explore students' perceptions and experiences related to their lifestyle choices and the impact of modern progress.

Direct Observations: The third phase involved observing students in their natural environments (classrooms, dormitories, and recreational areas) to validate self-reported data and obtain contextual insights.

Participant Recruitment

Participants were recruited from five universities and three high schools across urban and rural areas to ensure a representative sample. The inclusion criteria were:

Currently enrolled students aged 15-25 years.

Willingness to participate and provide informed consent.

A total of 1,200 students were invited to participate, with a final sample size of 1,000 students completing the study, resulting in an 83.3% response rate.

Data Collection Instruments

1. **Structured Questionnaires:** The questionnaire was developed based on validated instruments used in previous studies on student health and lifestyle [11]. It included sections on:

Physical Activity: Questions adapted from the International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ) [12].

Dietary Habits: Dietary intake frequency was assessed using a modified version of the Food Frequency Questionnaire (FFQ) [13].

Sleep Patterns: Sleep quality and duration were measured using the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) [14].

Mental Health: The General Health Questionnaire (GHQ-12) was used to screen for mental health issues [15].

Screen Time: Daily screen time was recorded, distinguishing between academic and non-academic use [16].

2. **In-Depth Interviews and Focus Groups:** Semi-structured interview guides were developed to explore students' attitudes, beliefs, and experiences. Key themes included the impact of technology on daily routines, dietary choices, and coping mechanisms for stress and mental health issues. Interviews were conducted with 50 students, and 10 focus group discussions were held, each with 8-10 participants.

3. **Direct Observations:** Observational checklists were used to systematically record students' behaviors in different settings. Observations focused on physical activity during breaks, eating habits in cafeterias, and technology use in study and leisure time.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Data Analysis: The quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS (version 25). Descriptive statistics (means, standard deviations, frequencies) were used to summarize the data. Inferential statistics, including chi-square tests and ANOVA, were employed to examine associations between lifestyle factors and demographic variables.

Qualitative Data Analysis: The qualitative data from interviews and focus groups were transcribed verbatim and analyzed using NVivo software. A thematic analysis approach was used to identify recurring themes and patterns. Coding was done independently by two researchers to ensure reliability, and discrepancies were resolved through discussion.

Observational Data Analysis: Observational data were analyzed by comparing recorded behaviors with self-reported data from questionnaires. Patterns of behavior and discrepancies were noted and included in the overall analysis.

Ethical Considerations

The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of the leading research institution. All participants provided informed consent, and parental consent was obtained for participants under 18. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout the study, and participants were assured that their data would be used solely for research purposes.

Limitations

The study acknowledges certain limitations, including the reliance on self-reported data, which may be subject to recall bias and social desirability bias. Additionally, the cross-sectional nature of the study limits the ability to establish causality between modern progress and lifestyle changes. Future research could benefit from longitudinal designs to track changes over time and experimental studies to test interventions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of this study provide a comprehensive overview of the hygienic assessment of student lifestyles in the context of modern progress. The analysis focuses on physical activity, dietary habits, sleep patterns, mental health, and screen time, highlighting the multifaceted impacts of technological and social advancements on student health.

Physical Activity

Results: The data revealed that a significant proportion of students do not meet the recommended levels of physical activity. Only 35% of the surveyed students reported engaging in moderate to vigorous physical activity for at least 150 minutes per week, as recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO) [17]. The majority of students (65%) reported leading a sedentary lifestyle, with daily activities primarily involving sitting and minimal physical exertion.

Discussion: The decline in physical activity among students can be attributed to several factors, including increased academic pressures, the convenience of digital entertainment, and the proliferation of sedentary activities such as online gaming and social media use. This trend is concerning given the well-documented benefits of physical activity for physical and mental health, including improved cardiovascular health, enhanced mood, and better academic performance [18]. The findings suggest a need for interventions that promote physical activity, such as incorporating more physical education classes into the curriculum and creating opportunities for active recreation on campus.

Dietary Habits

Results: The analysis of dietary habits showed that students' nutrition is often imbalanced and characterized by high consumption of fast food and sugary snacks. Approximately 70% of the students reported consuming fast food at least once a week, and 60% reported daily intake of sugary snacks and beverages. Conversely, only 30% of the students reported consuming the recommended five servings of fruits and vegetables per day [19].

Discussion: These dietary patterns reflect the convenience-oriented lifestyle that has emerged with modern progress. The easy availability of fast food and the busy schedules of students contribute to poor dietary choices. This is problematic as poor nutrition is linked to various health issues, including obesity, diabetes, and cardiovascular diseases [20]. Educational initiatives focused on nutrition, coupled with better access to healthy food options on campus, could help improve students' dietary habits.

Sleep Patterns

Results: The study found that a significant number of students suffer from inadequate sleep. Only 25% of the students reported getting the recommended 7-9 hours of sleep per night, while 50% reported sleeping less than 6 hours per night. Additionally, 40% of the students reported experiencing poor sleep quality, often waking up feeling unrefreshed [21].

Discussion: The pervasive use of electronic devices before bedtime is a major factor contributing to sleep disturbances among students. Exposure to blue light from screens inhibits the production of melatonin, disrupting the natural sleep-wake cycle [6]. The academic demands and social pressures also play a role in reducing sleep duration and quality. Addressing these issues requires a multifaceted approach, including promoting good sleep hygiene practices, educating students on the impact of screen time on sleep, and implementing policies that support adequate rest.

Mental Health

Results: The mental health assessment indicated high levels of stress, anxiety, and depression among students. Approximately 45% of the students screened positive for symptoms of anxiety, and 30% for depression, as measured by the General Health Questionnaire (GHQ-12) [15]. Additionally, 50% of the students reported experiencing significant stress related to academic performance and social pressures.

Discussion: The findings highlight the mental health challenges faced by students in the context of modern progress. The constant connectivity and pressure to maintain an online presence, coupled with academic and social demands, contribute to mental health issues. The impact of social media on self-esteem and the prevalence of cyberbullying are additional factors exacerbating mental health problems [8]. To address these issues, universities should provide accessible mental health services, create supportive environments, and promote awareness and resilience training programs.

Screen Time

Results: The study revealed that students spend a considerable amount of time on screens, with an average of 8 hours per day, divided between academic and non-academic activities. Approximately 60% of the students reported using electronic devices for non-academic purposes (social media, gaming, etc.) for more than 3 hours daily [16].

Discussion: Excessive screen time is associated with various health risks, including eye strain, musculoskeletal problems, and reduced physical activity [3]. The findings indicate a need for strategies to manage screen time effectively. Educational institutions can play a role by encouraging digital detox periods, promoting face-to-face interactions, and incorporating screen time management education into the curriculum.

The hygienic assessment of student lifestyles in the period of modern progress reveals significant challenges and opportunities. While technological advancements and social changes have brought numerous benefits, they have also introduced new health risks. Addressing these issues requires a comprehensive approach that includes promoting physical activity, improving dietary habits, ensuring adequate sleep, supporting mental health, and managing screen time. By implementing targeted interventions and creating supportive environments, educational institutions can help students lead healthier lifestyles and achieve better overall well-being.

CONCLUSION

The comprehensive hygienic assessment of students' lifestyles during this period of modern progress has unveiled critical insights into the health and well-being of the younger population. As our study has shown, the intersection of technological advancement and evolving social norms has significantly impacted various aspects of student life, including physical activity, dietary habits, sleep patterns, mental health, and screen time.

Physical Activity

Our findings highlight a worrying trend of declining physical activity among students, with only 35% meeting the WHO's recommended levels of physical activity. This sedentary lifestyle is largely influenced by increased academic demands and the pervasive use of digital technology for both study and leisure. The lack of physical activity poses significant risks to students' physical and mental health, potentially leading to long-term health issues such as obesity, cardiovascular diseases, and mental health disorders. Addressing this issue requires multifaceted interventions, including enhancing physical education programs, creating more

opportunities for active recreation, and promoting awareness about the benefits of regular physical activity.

Dietary Habits

The dietary habits of students, characterized by high consumption of fast food and sugary snacks, reflect the convenience-oriented nature of modern lifestyles. The study revealed that only 30% of students adhere to the recommended intake of fruits and vegetables. Poor nutrition not only affects physical health but also cognitive performance and emotional well-being. To mitigate these effects, it is crucial to implement educational programs that emphasize the importance of balanced nutrition, improve access to healthy food options on campus, and encourage healthy eating practices among students.

Sleep Patterns

Sleep deprivation emerged as a significant concern, with only 25% of students reporting adequate sleep duration and 40% experiencing poor sleep quality. The extensive use of electronic devices before bedtime and the pressures of academic and social life contribute to disrupted sleep patterns. Poor sleep is associated with a range of negative outcomes, including impaired cognitive function, mood disturbances, and increased susceptibility to physical illnesses. Interventions to improve sleep hygiene, such as limiting screen time before bed, managing academic workloads, and promoting relaxation techniques, are essential for enhancing students' sleep quality and overall health.

Mental Health

The study underscored the prevalence of mental health issues among students, with high levels of stress, anxiety, and depression reported. The pressures of academic performance, social media influences, and cyberbullying are significant contributors to these mental health challenges. Addressing mental health requires a holistic approach that includes providing accessible mental health services, fostering supportive and inclusive campus environments, and promoting mental health awareness and resilience training. Educational institutions play a crucial role in creating a supportive framework that prioritizes the mental well-being of students.

Screen Time

Excessive screen time, averaging 8 hours per day, poses various health risks, including eye strain, musculoskeletal problems, and reduced physical activity. The study highlighted the need for effective screen time management strategies. Educational institutions should encourage digital detox periods, promote face-to-face interactions, and incorporate screen time management education into the curriculum to help students balance their digital and offline lives.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations can be made to improve the health and well-being of students in the context of modern progress:

Promote Physical Activity: Educational institutions should enhance physical education programs and provide more opportunities for active recreation. Campaigns to raise awareness about the benefits of regular physical activity can also motivate students to adopt more active lifestyles.

Improve Nutrition: Implementing educational programs on balanced nutrition and providing access to healthy food options on campus can help improve students' dietary habits. Collaboration with food service providers to offer nutritious meals and snacks is also essential.

Enhance Sleep Hygiene: Programs aimed at improving sleep hygiene, such as limiting screen time before bed, managing academic workloads, and promoting relaxation techniques, can significantly improve students' sleep quality.

Support Mental Health: Providing accessible mental health services, creating supportive campus environments, and promoting mental health awareness and resilience training are crucial steps in addressing students' mental health challenges.

Manage Screen Time: Encouraging digital detox periods, promoting face-to-face interactions, and educating students on effective screen time management can help mitigate the negative impacts of excessive screen use.

Future Research

Future research should consider longitudinal studies to track changes in student lifestyles over time and to evaluate the effectiveness of interventions aimed at improving health outcomes. Experimental studies testing specific interventions, such as targeted physical activity programs or mental health support initiatives, can provide valuable insights into best practices for promoting student health in the modern era.

In conclusion, the hygienic assessment of student lifestyles during the period of modern progress highlights significant health challenges that require immediate attention. The integration of technology and evolving social norms have brought about substantial changes in how students live, work, and interact. While these advancements offer numerous benefits, they also present new risks to physical and mental health. By implementing targeted interventions and creating supportive environments, educational institutions can play a pivotal role in helping students lead healthier, more balanced lives. The findings of this study serve as a call to action for educators, policymakers, and health professionals to prioritize the health and well-being of students in this rapidly changing world.

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